

Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure (LASF4RI) initiative

Title:

The South American Gravitational wave Observatory (SAGO) White Paper

Thematic Areas:

Cosmology and Gravitation
Gravitational Wave Astrophysics

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Abstract:

Gravitational Wave Astrophysics became a reality with GW150914, when the final orbits of a binary black hole system were detected in the gravitational wave channel in 2015. Less than two years later, the GW170817 observation inaugurated the Multimessenger Astronomy involving gravitational waves. LIGO and Virgo in their advanced versions are currently in their third observing run (O3), which is planned to end in April 2020. KAGRA will join O3 soon and all three will be observing during two more periods (O4 and O5), with LIGO-India joining the network during O5, in 2025.

After 2030, it is likely that two other observatories will step in: Einstein Telescope (ET) and Cosmic Explorer. They will be the first ones of the so called third generation (3G). They will need a third partner for triangulation of arrival times in order to determine more precisely the source position in the sky. So, there will be an opportunity for a South American Gravitational wave Observatory, if the Latin American community reach by that time a critical mass of experimentalists already educated in the 3G technology. It could not be more timely then to start involving Latin American students and post-docs in the 3G technology now.

Scientific Context:

Gravitational Wave Astrophysics became a reality since GW150914, when the final orbits of a binary black hole system were detected in the gravitational wave spectrum in 2015. Less than two years later, the GW170817 observation inaugurated the Multimessenger Astronomy involving gravitational waves with the observation of a binary neutron star inspiral. Until the present, 10 binary black hole mergers have been announced and many more have already been detected and will be also announced soon. LIGO and Virgo in their advanced versions are in the third observing run (O3), which is planned to end in April 2020, with KAGRA joining them close do the end. All three will observe in two more periods (O4 and O5), with LIGO-India joining them in 2025. LIGO A+ and LIGO Voyager will be updates, which will reach higher sensitivities in the late 20's and early 30's.

After 2030 two other observatories will step in: Einstein Telescope (ET) (<http://www.et-gw.eu>) and Cosmic Explorer (<https://cosmicexplorer.org>). They will have sensitivities about 10 times higher than aLIGO and aVirgo (it means they will cover a volume in the Universe 1000 times larger) and will be the first ones of the so called third generation (3G). They will need a third partner for triangulation of arrival times in order to more precisely determine the source position in the sky. So, there will be an opportunity for a South American Gravitational wave Observatory.

A gravitational wave observatory in South America will be essential to move the Latin American scientific community to a new level in astronomy.

Objectives:

The main goal is the construction and the subsequent operation of a 3G laser interferometer for gravitational wave observation in South America. To reach this very ambitious goal the first step is undoubtedly the building of a local community with enough expertise in experimental activities and data analysis.

It is then crucial at this stage to train a large and widespread scientific community interested in gravitational wave astrophysics in Latin American countries, starting to involve more Latin American students and post-docs in the 3G technology.

Methodology:

At this stage it is crucial to have fellowships and research funding for creating a critical mass of researchers in Latin America with knowledge on the 3G technology, as well as attracting researchers already involved in 3G detector to visit regularly Latin America institutions to be involved in the training project.

In this way, it is essential to involve Latin American students and post-docs in the present projects:

LIGO (<https://www.ligo.org>),
Virgo (<http://www.virgo-gw.eu>),
KAGRA (<https://gwcenter.icrr.u-tokyo.ac.jp/en/>),
LIGO India (<http://www.gw-indigo.org/tiki-index.php>),
ET (<http://www.et-gw.eu>),
And Cosmic Explorer (<https://cosmicexplorer.org>)

and attract them and foreign researchers with knowledge on third generation detectors to shape research groups in Latin America.

We plan to involve the students and post-docs in the 3G R&D, which is divided in the following topics

(<https://gwic.ligo.org/3Gsubcomm/>,
https://gwic.ligo.org/3Gsubcomm/documents/GWIC_3G_R_D_Subcommittee_report_July_2019.pdf):

Facilities & Infrastructure,
Core Optics,
Coatings,
Cryogenics,
Newtonian Noise,
Light Sources,
Quantum Enhancements,
SAS & SUS,
Auxiliary Optics,
Simulation and Controls,
Calibration.

List of the interested scientists in the community:

1) Latin American people or people in Latin American countries already working in gravitational wave detection collaborations with laser interferometer technique:

Odylio D. Aguiar (LIGO)
Fabian Peña Arellano (KAGRA)
Márcio Constâncio Jr. (LIGO)
César Augusto Costa (LIGO)
Mario Diaz (LIGO)
Tábata A. Ferreira (LIGO)
Gabiela Gonzalez (LIGO)
Max Isi (LIGO)
Claudia Moreno (LIGO)
Marcos A. Okada (LIGO)
Riccardo Sturani (LIGO)
Enzo Tapia (Virgo)
and a few more.

2) Other people interested and/or already working in Gravitational Wave Astrophysics:

Carlos Filipe da Silva Costa
Herman Julio Mosquera Cuesta

Carlos Eduardo Cedeño Montana
Marc Casals Casanellas
Márcio Eduardo da Silva Alves
Marcelle Soares dos Santos
Elvis Camilo Ferreira
Rubens de Melo Marinho Junior
José Carlos Neves de Araujo
Massimo Tinto
Carlos Frajuca
Ívano Damião Soares
Nadja Simão Magalhães
Fábio da Silva Bortoli
Cecilia Bertoni Martha Hadler Chirenti
Henrique Pereira de Oliveira
Oswaldo Duarte Miranda
Jaziel Goulart Coelho
José Antônio de Freitas Pacheco
Mario Novello
Reuven Opher
Fernando Kokubun
Eduardo dos Santos Pereira
José Ademir Sales de Lima
Alberto Saa
Raissa Mendes
Nei Fernandes de Oliveira Jr.
German Lugones
Anderson Campos Fauth
Joaquim José Barroso
Samuel Rocha de Oliveira
Rogério Moraes Oliveira
Kilder Leite Ribeiro
César Henrique Lenzi
Sérgio Turano de Souza
Xavier Gratens
João Braga
Claudia Vilega Rodrigues
Vincenzo Liccardo
Helmo Alan Batista de Araújo
Bruno Gonçalves
Fabio Rogério Longen
Leandro Herculano da Silva
César Oswaldo Vasquez Flores
Cesar Strauss
Lázaro Aparecido Pires de Camargo
Alan Braga Cassiano

And many other researchers and professors working on GR, gravitational waves and astronomy/astrophysics.

Current status and expected challenges:

There are only two groups in Latin America involved in the LIGO Scientific Collaboration (LSC) and one in Virgo. All three groups are in Brazil. And there are only a few Latin Americans involved in laser interferometer projects. Therefore, the challenges to overcome in order to propose a project for the construction and development of a gravitational wave observatory in South America are enormous.

Timeline:

The present proposal is a long term one, aiming the future of the gravitational wave astronomy in the Latin America. During the next decade (20's) we need to send students and post-docs to work on gravitational wave collaborations using the laser technique and try to form groups in Latin American countries with foreign post-docs educated in the 3G technology or with the students and post-docs that were sent to those groups.

The present groups and the newly formed groups in Latin America should start 3G R&D activities in collaboration with the other worldwide collaborations.

Also, during this period, seismic studies should be conducted to search for possible sites in South America. There are already a few regions to search. According to the IAG-USP seismic group there are three low seismic activity regions in South America:

- Interior of Uruguay and Rio Grande do Sul state,
- Interior of São Paulo and Mato Grosso do Sul states,
- The "Triângulo das Secas" in the Brazilian northeast, which includes the region around the city of Irecê, which does not have rivers.

There are two other interesting regions in South America, even though they are not seismically calm:

- The Uyuni salt flat,
- The AUGER facility.

Then, after a critical mass of researchers with knowledge of the 3G technology is presented in Latin America, a proposal for the construction of SAGO can be made to all possible Latin American science foundations in collaboration with the other 3G projects.

Construction and operational costs:

The budget can be roughly estimated to be in the range of US\$ 1-2 billion.

Computing requirements:

These are going to be given by the present Cosmic Explorer and ET R&D studies.